

FINAL REPORT

IMPACT ASSESSMENT

of the Energy Model Region
NEFI – New Energy for Industry

Project team

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ABSTRACT

The NEFI (New Energy for Industry) Impact Assessment, commissioned by the Climate and Energy Fund (KLIEN) and conducted by AIT with support from MUL, evaluates the contributions of NEFI projects in advancing Austria's industrial decarbonisation efforts. The assessment aligns with NEFI's core objectives: (1) reducing industrial carbon emissions, (2) fostering local value creation through Austrian technology, and (3) increasing the resilience of the Austrian industry in energy supply, processes and infrastructure. This study assesses completed or nearly completed NEFI projects, capturing both quantitative and qualitative impacts. A robust and widely applicable methodology was developed to quantify the potential impact of a technological or systemic solution if rolled-out on three dimensions (in agreement with the NEFI goals as well as Austrian and EU targets):

- Climate impact: Quantified through CO₂ reductions, considering measures such as fuel switching, energy efficiency, carbon capture, and circular economy.
- Macroeconomic impact: Captured in GDP contributions (CAPEX, OPEX and export revenues).
- Resilience: Analysed qualitatively due to varying definitions across projects, with fossil energy reduction as the primary quantitative KPI.

The first wave of NEFI solutions, requiring approximately €2 billion in capital, can achieve a 53% reduction in CO₂ emissions in participating sectors until 2040, addressing critical decarbonisation needs cost-effectively. These preliminary outcomes represent only the more accessible "low-hanging fruit" and can only be realised with favorable conditions, including supportive regulatory frameworks, targeted policies, and significant funding. Future projects are expected to entail greater investment but will also yield substantial, scalable results. The results of the impact assessment feed into the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios ([NEFI Decarbonisation Scenarios](#)), helping to identify key thematic areas (levers of action, NEFI Innovation Hubs) where new research projects will be developed to accelerate the industrial decarbonisation.

The methodology developed in this project will be extended to all NEFI projects as well as to projects funded by the FTI initiative for Transforming Industry.

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1 BACKGROUND AND GOAL

The Impact Assessment is a project commissioned by the Climate and Energy Fund (KLIEN) to AIT, with MUL as subcontractor, aiming to capture the impact of the energy model region NEFI – New Energy for Industry. In the initial phase, a methodology was developed to assess the impact along three key dimensions: (i) climate impact, (ii) macroeconomic effects, and (iii) resilience. These dimensions align with the goals of the NEFI program (1 - the decarbonisation of the industrial energy systems, 2 - value creation by technology made in Austria and 3 - securing Austria's position as an industry location through user involvement) as well as with the national and EU objectives. Our in-depth analysis goes beyond quantitative indicators: it also encompasses non-quantifiable outcomes, risks, regulatory obstacles, and hurdles associated with each project. Both qualitative and quantitative findings are reported here in order to provide a comprehensive understanding of NEFI's impact.

This impact analysis includes all finalised projects or these nearing completion, together with corresponding model solutions. The comprehensiveness of this evaluation aims at measuring the full spectrum of NEFI's impact.

One notable contribution from NEFI has been the development of decarbonisation scenarios for the Austrian manufacturing industries, which provide the quantitative framework and principles of this Impact Assessment.

We proceeded in three work packages:

WP 1 - method development and testing on selected pilots.

WP 2 - harmonisation of the methodology across the three model regions

WP 3 - execution of Impact Assessment

A similar project was concurrently underway in the other energy model regions, WIVA P&G and Green Energy Lab, which necessitated regular coordination in terms of key performance indicators (KPIs) and methodology. While efforts were made to maintain methodological consistency across regions, the unique characteristics of each area required adjustments, particularly in certain dimensions and at a detailed level.

For feedback as well as strategic and methodological input, an advisory board has been established, consisting of the funding body KLIEN together with representatives of the Federal Ministry for Climate Action (BMK) and of the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG).

2 APPROACH AND TIMELINE

The focus of the first project period (covered in WP1 & WP2) was to define a robust methodology encompassing all projects' impact dimensions and provide for robust scaling of the results in alignment with the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios.

The key performance indicators (KPIs) were defined along the three main dimensions (A) ecological impact, (B) macro-economic impact and (C) resilience, where resilience is assessed partly quantitatively, as the contribution of the projects to this dimension is highly diverse and could not be represented sufficiently by a single indicator or projected on a single quantitative scale. Subsequently, these KPIs were tested in two pilot cases. Since the KPIs and the method were showing promising first results, it was possible to roll out the method for in total 7 sub-projects and their associated model solutions.

In the second project phase (covered in WP3), the methodology was applied to all projects that had progressed so far as to provide data. In this manner it was possible to assess the impact of 14 out of 24 projects of NEFI.

The high-level concept of the impact assessment methodology can be seen in **Figure 1**:

Figure 1: Concept of the impact assessment

The detailed project timeline is shown in the following Gantt (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Gantt chart of project timeline

Table 1: Milestone plan

Milestones	Scheduled date	Achieved on
1. Kick-off meeting	Q4 2022	18.01.2023
2. First advisory board meeting	Q1 2023	06.07.2023
3. Results from pilot cases	Q2-Q3 2023	Q2-Q3 2023
4. Interim report	Q3 2023	30.09.2023
5. Second advisory board meeting	Q1 2024 ¹	
6. Presentation of results and closing event	Q4 2024	

Overall, the impact assessment met the planned timeline. The official kick-off meeting took place on 18th January 2023 and the first advisory board meeting on 6th July 2023. As scheduled the project was completed by November 2024.

¹ The 2nd advisory board meeting was shifted in accordance with KLIEN and B.A.U.M. Consult to Q4/2024.

3 IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

Assessing the potential impact of a research project is, by its very nature, a hypothetical task. This study is specifically focused on addressing that challenge: it aims to quantify the possible future benefits that may arise from the knowledge gained through NEFI research projects, considering three distinct dimensions. It is important to note that the goal of this analysis is not to evaluate the immediate, tangible outcomes of the projects – such as the direct impact on carbon emissions as a result of the project activities. Instead, the emphasis lies on understanding the broader, long-term potential of the solutions generated. By shifting the focus away from short-term or direct outputs, this approach allows for a more comprehensive assessment of the solutions’ possible contributions to the three NEFI goals: climate neutrality, value creation & securing production sites and resilience.

Thus, in accordance with national and EU targets and legislation (e.g. green deal and taxonomy regulation) and the core NEFI goals, the following indicators have been defined for the three dimensions of impact:

- (A) **Climate impact** is reported in the form of reduced tons CO₂, for instance due to measures contributing to the four “key levers of action” as defined in the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios (see **Figure 3**):
 - a. Fuel switching to carbon-neutral gases (hydrogen, bio- and synthetic CH₄) and biomass
 - b. Energy efficiency, and low-emission electrification
 - c. Carbon capture technologies with further sequestration or permanent utilisation
 - d. Circular use of materials and decreasing raw material demand
- (B) **Macro-economic impact** is defined as the contribution of the technology or solution to the gross domestic product. This includes the revenue generated by exports of the technology, the national capital expenditure (CAPEX) as well as the national operative expenditure (OPEX)
- (C) **Resilience**: from the great diversity of projects, a KPI encompassing all aspects of resilience could not be found. Therefore, it has been decided that on a quantitative level, reduction of fossil energy is counted only, plus other aspects are summarised on a qualitative basis.

LEVERS OF ACTION

Figure 3: NEFI levers of action according to the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios (left). NEFI sub-projects contributing to the levers of action and their impact (right).

3.1 Analytic approach: impact elicitation and measurement

NEFI projects have diverse research questions, spanning the development of concrete technologies to systemic decarbonisation solutions for entire areas. In order to elicit the (potential) impact of each project, all its innovation aspects have to be analysed in all three KPI dimensions. This was done as follows:

- (1) From interviews with the project leader as well as from the project reports the core innovation aspects or **specific solutions** are identified. Specific solutions are chosen as the basis entity for the impact assessment due to their higher level of granularity, which is essential for accurate and reliable scaling of effects. Moreover, defining these solutions facilitates cross-checking across sub-projects, helping to prevent double counting and, consequently, the overestimation of impacts.
- (2) Each of these core innovation aspects are analysed for their **impact** in each KPI dimension. If an impact could be demonstrated in the project, it is quantified in the context of the project scope (e.g. energy demand of the process and savings).
- (3) Relying on literature research as well as data from the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios, the effect of each specific solution is **scaled** up from project scope to industry sector and national level as further explained below. Key assumptions such as emission factors, market size, growth and diffusion are afflicted with some uncertainties. Therefore, this step is central to the reliability of the result. Often just orders of magnitude of an effect can be given, and some projects' contribution in one KPI can be larger than other projects' by a factor of 100 or more. Hence, the substantiality of each solution's impact is assessed and the diligence of research for its scale-up suitably adapted. This last step ensures that these effects that move the KPI dial receive most diligence and their error is minimised.
- (4) The **sum** of the effects of the specific solutions, scaled up on national level for each KPI is reported as the impact of the model region.

To simplify the admittedly complex methodology, we applied it to the hypothetical project "Nail It." This "fun project" explores the research question: How can photovoltaic (PV) panels be mounted on trees? The project investigates various solutions, some of which are quantifiable and thus covered by the impact assessment. Additionally, the solutions are scalable, as the installation of panels can be extended to other trees beyond the initial project scope. NEFI is responsible for assessing the impact and can take credit for this achievement. However, overlap with another project, "Screw It"—where panels are screwed rather than nailed—needs to be considered to avoid double counting. The decision tree in **Figure 4** provides a very simplified overview of these steps.

Figure 4: Interview questions explained with the hypothetical example project “Nail It”. Three specific solutions were developed in this “fun project” to answer the research question “How to mount a solar panel on a tree”. These specific solutions are then evaluated to decide if they are suitable for the NEFI Impact Assessment.

3.2 Scaling of project results and model solutions (WP1)

Typically, the direct effect of a NEFI project itself in terms of GHG emissions reduced, GDP, or resilience gain is limited. Most projects focus on the proof-of-concept of a technological solution, or on the demonstration of such solutions on a low to medium technological readiness level (TRL). However, the solutions can have significant impact if implemented on a larger or full scale. As the diffusion of a technology with time is highly nonlinear, often sigmoidal, a practical solution can have a massive impact, though its full effects often become clear only later in its maturation cycle. Herein lies the true impact of the model region: the network of both researchers and applying industry has the potential to significantly accelerate this diffusion and provide a highly agile environment to innovate much quicker. However, due to the inherent uncertainties of new technologies, scaling the possible impact depends on several assumptions with rather high error. Therefore, the diffusion rates were carefully and conservatively chosen (taking into account market size and potential development) in close alignment with project leaders and experts. To avoid overestimating a solution's potential, the scaling factor was divided into two components (each <1): the diffusion rate, reflecting the applicability of the technology, and a factor representing the fundamental applicability of the technology along with the presence of other high-TRL competitive technologies for the same application in a given market or environment. For example, not as many smelters or kilns are expected to implement Oxyfuel technology, although the technology could fulfill given process requirements.

As depicted in **Figure 5**, the scaling occurs in two steps along the three dimensions (A – climate impact, B – macro-economic impact, C – resilience). The first step is intra-sectoral from one industrial site to all sites, the second step is cross-sectoral from one sector to all other sectors within Austria where the technology or solution can be applied.

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Figure 5: Schematics of scaling process

To avoid overestimating the impact of the solutions and the model region, the scaling effect is dampened by a project-specific diffusion factor δ_i .

In addition, the effect of solutions and levers are set conservatively using the Pathway of Industry (POI) scenario from the decarbonisation scenarios ([Pathway to industrial decarbonisation](#)) as an appropriate reference baseline. On top, cross-dependencies (albeit very few) were identified and accounted for by reducing the respective solutions diffusion factor.

The total impact I_{tot} of all NEFI projects per dimension is calculated as

$$I_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{t=2025}^{2040} I_i(t) \cdot \frac{S_{i,tot}}{S_i} \cdot \delta_i(t) dt$$

with the variables

I_{tot}	...total cumulated impact of all NEFI projects
$I_i(t)$...time dependent impact of NEFI project i
n	...number of evaluated NEFI projects
$S_{i,tot}$...total scale basis in Austria of NEFI project i
S_i	...scale basis of NEFI project i
$\frac{S_{i,tot}}{S_i}$...scaling factor of NEFI project i
$\delta_i(t)$...time dependent diffusion factor of NEFI project i .

Due to data availability restrictions, the integral is numerically approximated by linearly interpolating the integration range in five-year intervals.

The total impact is calculated for every dimension, resulting in the following index numbers:

$I_{CO_2e,tot}$...climate impact in Mt of CO ₂ e saved
$I_{me,tot}$...macroeconomic impact in M€
$I_{res,tot}$...resilience impact in TWh of imported energy saved.

In order to avoid double counting of follow-up projects or projects addressing the same target group or sector, the projects are grouped and scaled together.

To simplify the explanation of the three KPI dimensions, the scaling and the diffusion of the solution, we will return to the hypothetical example project "Nail It" (see **Figure 6**). The specific solution of nailing PV panels onto trees has an impact across all three dimensions:

- 1) **Climate Impact:** By generating renewable energy through the PV panels, CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels can be avoided. The specific impact (10 kg CO₂ per panel per year) is scaled by the number of trees equipped with panels, though not all trees can be used for this purpose due to various limitations. Therefore, estimating the potential is critical, and care must be taken to avoid overestimating the total potential. Additionally, the estimation of the diffusion factor, which represents the rate of implementation (i.e., how quickly the solution can be deployed), is the second and highly critical step in the impact assessment. It requires careful consideration to avoid errors in forecasting the actual rate of adoption. The cumulative impact is then calculated based on these factors.
- 2) **Macroeconomic Impact:** We assume that only the nails used for mounting the panels are produced in Austria, contributing to the national economy. Additionally, local labor is involved in the installation process. Since the solution is highly effective, there is potential for exporting this technology, meaning that the nails and the know-how (licencing) could also contribute to international trade.
- 3) **Resilience Impact:** By using PV panels, the need for importing fossil fuels is reduced, which in turn promotes energy independence for the location. This impact is expressed in terms of the amount of energy produced (in kWh).

Figure 6 Questioning framework for Project leader interviews on project impact

For an example where this method is applied, see the appendix.

3.3 Alignment across model regions (WP2)

The three energy model regions are all conducting an impact assessment. Where possible the methodology as well as base assumptions are coordinated. In order to ensure maximal alignment, regular coordination meetings take place with representatives of accompanying research B.A.U.M Consult as sparring partners. As specified in the offer, an advisory board for all three model regions' impact assessments has been established with representatives of the Ministry of Climate Action and Energy (BMK), the Climate and Energy Fund (KLIEN) and the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG). The first meeting took place as scheduled on 6th July 2023 (T2.2). The following organisations were represented:

The advisory board approved the presented methodology for the Impact Assessment of the three model regions. Additionally, the point was raised that other potential negative impacts should be incorporated into the assessment. It was confirmed that this will be done qualitatively.

In the next advisory board meeting (scheduled as per offer in Q1/2024, in alignment with KLIEN shifted to Q4/2024 i.o.t. report results there) each model region will present its results including risks (qualitatively) as well as recommendations for funding agencies on the methodology and the effort required for such an assessment in order to potentially incorporate it in future calls. This will include adequate push-factors to drive such an impact assessment in programs containing several or many sub-projects.

4 PROJECTS ASSESSED

So far, 14 out of 24 NEFI sub-projects have been assessed quantitatively. Three projects have been assessed, but their results not counted in the overall impact: The NEFI_Lab project, being an innovation lab, cannot be assessed due to its unique nature. The project Gmunden High Temperature Heat Link R&D has been assessed but due to lack of likely multiplication excluded, see section 4.6. LEAP, a project already completed, was evaluated alongside its follow-up project, AHEAD, which is also currently running but will be assessed within the new NEFI+ framework, together with the other still missing projects. All other projects are still in progress and have not yet yielded specific solutions.

4.1 Key takeaways and levers of action

The key takeaways of the impacting projects and the corresponding levers of action are shown in the table below:

Table 4: Overview of key takeaways from projects and associated levers of action

Project	Key Takeaways	Levers of Action
Biochar for industry	Sustainable biochar as a substitute for fossil charcoal in metallurgy, generating clean electricity and heat, with inland investment in production and export potential for biochar systems.	CO ₂ -neutral gases and biomass, Electrification and energy efficiency.
CE4T	Optimised energy use and integration of renewable energy in skiing regions, better data collection, reduction of power peaks.	Electrification and energy efficiency.
EDCSproof	Energy Demand Control System increase energy efficiency through optimised system control, significant energy and emission savings from waste heat recovery via heat pumps.	Electrification and energy efficiency.
EDDY	Enhanced drying process with real-time control leading to energy and emission savings, improved product quality, reduced wastage.	Electrification and energy efficiency.
Green Bricks	Use of electric kiln leading to energy savings and emission reductions, secured jobs, export opportunities.	Electrification and energy efficiency, Circular economy.
Heat Highway	Interregional heat transfer networks (HTN) were developed using waste heat to reduce natural gas use, supported by a feasibility study and investment in waste heat recovery.	CO ₂ -neutral gases and biomass, Electrification and energy efficiency.
HySTePs	An innovative hybrid steam storage concept was developed, increasing storage capacity by 30%, with key technical challenges	Electrification and energy efficiency.

	identified for commercialisation, and a patent filed alongside academic insights gained.	
InduGrid	Platform for industrial energy communities provides scalable energy solutions for waste heat recovery and optimal integration of renewable energy sources.	Electrification and energy efficiency.
OxySteel	Oxyfuel technology reduces emissions in steel and cement industries, potential for carbon capture.	Electrification and energy efficiency, Carbon capture.
SANBA	Waste heat usage in Austrian army barracks with heat pumps, leading to energy savings and emission reductions.	CO ₂ -neutral gases and biomass, Electrification and energy efficiency.
SBM_Ind	Promising business models for energy communities, promoting hydrogen sales, use of industrial waste heat, efficient energy distribution through energy hubs and increased flexibility in energy use.	Electrification and energy efficiency, CO ₂ -neutral gases and biomass.

4.1.1 Levers of Action for Climate-Neutral Industrial Energy Systems

In our projects, we have applied key levers of action to drive the transition to climate-neutral industrial energy systems. These levers, including electrification and energy efficiency, CO₂-neutral gases and biomass, carbon capture, and the circular economy, play an important role in reducing emissions and optimising resource use.

1) Energy Efficiency and Low-Emission Electrification

Energy efficiency and electrification played a critical role in reducing emissions across multiple projects. This was achieved through optimised energy use, enhanced system control, and improved processes like waste heat recovery and real-time monitoring. These efforts resulted in energy and emission savings, as well as enhanced productivity and product quality. Projects focusing on heat storage and advanced energy systems also contributed to significant efficiency gains, promoting more sustainable energy consumption and reducing dependence on conventional fuels (e.g., OxySteel, EDCSproof, EDDY, HySTePs).

2) Fuel Switching to CO₂-Neutral Gases and Biomass

Fuel switching is a vital lever in transitioning from fossil-based energy sources to carbon-neutral alternatives, such as hydrogen, bio- and synthetic methane, and biomass. By replacing fossil fuels with cleaner options, these projects led to substantial reductions in natural gas and fossil charcoal use, resulting in lower emissions and greater reliance on domestically produced energy. This strategy helped shift industries towards cleaner energy models and contributed to long-term sustainability (e.g., SANBA, SBM_Ind, Heat Highway, Biochar for Industry).

3) Carbon Capture and Storage/Utilisation (CCS/CCU)

Carbon capture technologies are increasingly recognised as a key lever to further reduce emissions, especially in high-carbon industries like steel and cement. The integration of CCS/CCU showed significant potential for reducing CO₂ emissions, aligning with broader decarbonisation efforts. While these technologies are still developing, they offer promising opportunities for future emission control and play a crucial role in achieving carbon neutrality (e.g., OxySteel).

4) Circular Economy

The circular economy focuses on increasing the use of end-of-life materials and utilising CO₂ as a resource for material production. By repurposing waste materials and promoting resource-efficient practices, this approach reduces reliance on raw materials, conserves valuable resources, and contributes to long-term environmental sustainability (e.g., Green Bricks, Biochar for Industry).

Conclusion

The application of the levers of action, such as electrification and energy efficiency, CO₂-neutral gases and biomass, carbon capture, and the circular economy, across various projects, showcases the diverse strategies employed to drive climate neutral industrial development and sustainability. These levers not only contributed to significant emission reductions but also created valuable economic benefits, such as increased

competitiveness, job security, and export opportunities, all of which promote a more sustainable and resilient industrial landscape.

4.2 Biochar for industry

4.2.1 Project goals

- Development of a process to produce biochar
- As value-added products of the process, green electricity and heat are intended to reduce CO₂ emissions from the energy sector
- CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) simulation-based optimisation of the pyrolysis process and development of pyrolysis gas treatment for heat and power generation
- Carrying out, analysing and evaluating test runs on a test system
- Development of application concepts in the metallurgical industry

4.2.2 Solutions developed

- Development of prototype for biochar production
- Biochar characterised and applications validated
- Case study carried out and analysed

4.2.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(A) Climate dimension

- reduced CO₂ emissions as sustainably produced charcoal is used instead of fossil charcoal for metallurgy

(B) Macro-economic dimension

- Inland investments
- Exports of biochar production system

(C) Resilience

- Dependency on fossil charcoal is reduced significantly as sustainably produced charcoal can be used

(D) Qualitative indicators

- Highly efficient production of green electricity and heat from pyrolysis gases as value-added of the biochar production
- Case studies to validate biochar approach

4.3 CE4T – Clean Energy 4 Tourism

4.3.1 Project goals

- Decarbonisation of the winter tourism industry using digitalisation technology and new optimisation algorithms
- Development of optimisation algorithms
- Demonstration and exploitation of the required flexibilities at all levels
- Energy monitoring to increase energy efficiency
- Integration of renewable energy production units in the overall system

4.3.2 Solutions developed

- Planning Tool – Energy Communities (see factsheet in Appendix)
- ENDOPT – Energy and Operation Optimisation (see factsheet in Appendix)
- Energy Monitoring Dashboard (see factsheet in Appendix)

4.3.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(A) Climate dimension

- Emission savings by optimised integration of renewable energy sources (RES)
- Energy savings by optimised ski lift operation
- Shifting electricity demand into times with lower grid emission factor

(B) Macro-economic dimension

- Project commission for optimisation of RES integration

(C) Resilience

- Energy savings by optimised ski lift operation

(D) Qualitative indicators

- Dashboard for customers
- Reduction of total power peak
- „Green“ image improving acceptance amid local population
- Increase of data collection
- Know how generated to use in other projects

For CE4T the scaling was carried out intra-sectorally from the partner ski resorts to all Austrian ski resorts above 1.000 m sea level.

Figure 7: Scaling steps for model solutions from CE4T project

4.4 EDCSproof – Energy Demand Control System – PROcess Optimisation for industrial low temperature systems

4.4.1 Project goals

- Integration of renewables into industrial low temperature systems by energy storage systems
- Waste heat use through high temperature heat pumps
- Online, predictive and holistic, reconfigurable control concept for energy demand in industrial processes
- Flexible industrial participants in power grids

4.4.2 Solutions developed

- Development of control system to integrate renewables into energy system and energy efficiency increase
- Installation of heat pumps for waste heat recovery

4.4.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(A) Climate dimension

- Emission savings by optimal control of energy system and therefore energy savings

(B) Macroeconomic dimension

- Implementation of control system incl. necessary controller hardware
- Annual license fee

(C) Resilience

- Energy savings by optimal control of system
- Energy savings by installation of heat pump
- Increased energy efficiency results in reduced gas demand. Effect varies strongly across industrial sectors thus cannot be quantified

(D) Qualitative indicators

- Patent registered for control system
- Further emission savings and macroeconomic effects by installation of heat pumps for waste heat recovery → effects are not included in KPIs since only the effect of the optimal control is considered NEFI result

Intra-sectoral scaling to Austrian food and beverage sector. Cross-sectoral includes wood, pulp & paper, chemical & petrochemical incl. pharmaceuticals, rubber and plastics. Macroeconomic effect scales with number of manufacturing sites in Austria, climate effect scales with emissions of the considered sectors.

4.5 EDDY – Enhanced Drying

4.5.1 Project goals

- Optimisation of industrial drying in the agricultural commodity and food industries

- Inline monitoring of product moisture in drying processes with novel, compact and cost-effective optical IR sensor technology that enables real-time control
- Optimised operating strategies based on numerical models and monitoring data (increase productivity, reduce CO₂ emissions and operating costs, ensure high product quality independent of external factors), designing measures to further increase energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources (e.g. heat pumps).

4.5.2 Solutions developed

- EDDY sensors: low-cost sensors for inline process analysis during drying
- EDDY toolbox: (webbased) tool for identification of optimisation potential of the drying process by using heat pumps. In a second step, the toolbox will be linked to a data base of suitable and available heat pumps.

4.5.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(A) Climate dimension

- Emission savings due to optimised drying processes using EDDY sensors

(B) Macroeconomic dimension

- Market potential of EDDY toolbox
- Market potential of EDDY sensors

(C) Resilience

- Energy savings due to optimised drying processes using the EDDY sensors

(D) Qualitative indicators

- Enhanced product quality due to moisture control using EDDY sensors
- Reduced product wastage due to moisture control using EDDY sensors

Drying and dehydration are among the most energy-intensive and widespread processes in industry and are currently based predominantly on fossil fuels. For the scaling, the energy demand for drying processes of the whole Austrian manufacturing sector was used.

4.6 Gmunden High Temperature Heat Link R&D

4.6.1 Project goals

- Implementation of waste heat utilisation with highest possible CO₂ reduction.
- Develop and evaluate concepts based on a mixture of innovative and proven technologies
- Comparison of dirty gas and clean gas solutions (hot gas filtration of cement kiln exhaust gas)
- Maximum decarbonisation of the entire system
- Cost-optimised use of heat storage solutions
- High temperature heat transport over 1.5 km of public land.

4.6.2 Solutions developed

- The cement plant Gmunden has a waste heat potential of about 10 MW-th at 400°C.
- Concepts and technologies are developed and analysed allowing the utilisation of flue gas heat.
- The waste heat can be transferred at a high temperature level via a 1.5 km long pipeline to large consumers in the urban area of Gmunden.

4.6.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(A) Climate dimension

- Reduced CO₂ emissions as less primary energy is needed at consumers' site

Scalability:

- High temperature flue gas heat recovery has multiple potential uses in the minerals and steel industry.
- On the sink-side it is necessary for medium temperature consumer demand to be situated within a few kilometers. This is not the case in many sites of these industries in Austria.
- But in general these high temperature production processes are “hard to abate”. In the given case of clinker production the only techno-economic feasible climate neutral option is carbon capture. That activity itself needs substantial amount of heat. Therefore (and by the general rule of prioritising intra-plant use before inter-plant use of waste heat), management decided not to implement the project.
- However, much of the gained knowledge on flue gas implementation technologies can and most probably will be used in a future carbon capture process.

Due to competing internal needs for the heat in the future for carbon sequestration, the potential of external heat use, as developed in this NEFI project, has not been included in the NEFI overall impact (in terms of the three KPIs).

4.7 Green Bricks

4.7.1 Project goals

- Holistic optimisation of the brick manufacturing process
- Development of new CO₂-neutral clay mixtures, considering site-specific product and clay properties as well as industrial production environments
- Optimisation of the overall energy efficiency in the dryer - burner - heat pump heat network and adaptation of the brick drying technology to the new electric kiln and the clay recipe
- Optimisation of the operation of the innovative, highly efficient, high-temperature tunnel kiln
- Scaling of the concept and assessment of transferability to other production sites and technology transfer to related sectors
- Securing social acceptance and trust in the solutions developed

4.7.2 Solutions developed

- Digital mapping of brickworks and evaluation of model for techno-economic optimisation
- Development of new CO₂-neutral clay mixtures
- Adaption and extension of the dryer control system
- Operation of highly efficient, electrically powered tunnel kiln

4.7.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(A) Climate dimension

- Reduced CO₂ emissions as less primary energy is needed with new highly efficient electrical kiln

(B) Macro-economic dimension

- Investments in new kiln

(C) Resilience

- New kiln can be operated with electricity instead of with natural gas and additives

(D) Qualitative indicators

- Jobs secured because of security of location: quantitative data is available but not included in the calculations to maintain consistency with other projects
- Techno-economic evaluation of further Wienerberger sites and know-how transfer within and outside the Wienerberger Group

4.8 Heat Highway

4.8.1 Project goals

- Elaboration of two 100 km long Heat Transmission Networks (HTN) in Upper Austria and Styria and advancement of three sections towards practical realisation: preparation of KPC investment funding applications for the Upper Austrian HTN sections “Zentralraum” and “Linz high-temperature network” and initialisation of next steps and stakeholder participation in Styria. Investigation of follower cases.
- Development a multi-level toolbox for optimising the interregional heat transmission networks (HTN) implementation and operation
- Anticipation of industrial waste heat potential from current and breakthrough processes in a decarbonisation scenario
- Development and prototyping of a cost-effective pipe system to significantly reduce the investment costs in HTN
- Setting up a 3D simulation-based "virtual HTN demonstrator" to demonstrate the feasibility of HTN systems despite their complexity

4.8.2 Solutions developed

- Development of a multi-level toolbox
- Lean pipe prototype development
- HTN Upper Austria section LINZ, Section ZENTRALRAUM, HTN Styria
- Follower cases & replicability (HTN Inntal in Tyrol, HTN Innviertel etc.)
- Virtual demonstrator

4.8.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

- (A) Climate dimension
 - Reduced CO₂ emissions due to lower energy consumption (oil savings, natural gas savings)
- (B) Macro-economic dimension
 - Future Investment costs
- (C) Resilience
 - Natural gas, oil and energy savings
- (D) Qualitative indicators
 - Increased supply reliability - diversification of the supply
 - Increased usage of waste heat
 - Utilisation of regional energy resources on supra-regional level

The Heat Highway project has not been scaled up because it is considered to be very specific, with its own set of technical, geographical, and economic aspects. In addition, framework conditions play an important role in determining the scalability of the project. These include regulatory requirements, the availability of appropriate infrastructure, the involvement of stakeholders, and potential financial constraints. Given these complexities, it was not possible to make reliable or generalised estimates for scaling up the project to a larger region or multiple locations.

4.9 HySTePs – Hybrid storage for efficient processes

4.9.1 Project goals

- Development and experiment test of an innovative hybrid storage concept in order to increase the storage capacity of a steam storage in operation up to 40 %
- Encasing of a laboratory scale steam accumulator in innovative latent heat storage elements.
- Development and implementation of heat conduction structures and state of charge measurement for the hybrid storage tank.
- Technoeconomic evaluation on the basis of five industrial processes in various sectors and a detailed needs analysis

4.9.2 Solutions developed

In the project HyStEPs a lab scale steam storage device was built and implemented into a steam network to carry out experiments with attached phase change material modules. These modules allowed an increase of the steam storage capacity of 30 %. Technical issues that were addressed in course of the project were: corrosion and thermal conductivity of the phase change material, heat transfer between the modules and the steam storage vessel, the control strategy of the resulting hybrid storage device, and techno-economic aspects.

The working principle of enhancing existing steam storage devices with latent heat storage material, i.e. PCM, was successfully demonstrated. However, this very first project in this field also showed currently existing challenges to make this technology market ready:

- i) for mass production a new approach for the encasing of PCM is necessary, which is less expensive
- ii) the heat transfer between the steam vessel and the module must be increased to increase performance
- iii) heat transfer within the PCM has to be increased in a clever way

4.9.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

- (D) Qualitative indicators
 - Patent and academic learnings out of development of innovative hybrid steam storage concept

4.10 InduGrid – Industrial Microgrids

4.10.1 Project goals

- Creation of a platform for the presentation of suitable industrial participants for an Energy Community in a spatial environment, considering the technical, business and legal framework.
- Application of the platform for industrial energy communities at three locations in Upper Austria (Wels, Ennschafen and Hagenberg) with different framework conditions such as electrical energy exchange, thermal exchange and combined thermal-electrical exchange
- Development of business models and their direct evaluation by means of simulations on the developed platform

- Evaluation of the socio-economic effects as well as the public benefit in terms of awareness raising and flexibility possibilities for companies, employees and end customers

4.10.2 Solutions developed

- Bilateral thermal exchange in alternative testbed in Wels
- Multilateral electrical energy exchange from the company Rübigen in Wels and its small hydropower plant to supply surrounding consumers
 - Multilateral energy exchange in the framework of citizen's energy communities in Wels and Hagenberg. Development of a business model / contractual structure for energy communities
 - Optimisation software developed
 - Visualisation in Energy Map
 - Conclusions for legislation

4.10.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

- (A) Climate dimension
 - Emission reduction due to waste heat usage and therefore energy (natural gas) savings
- (C) Resilience
 - Energy savings and therefore reduced demand of energy import due to waste heat usage
- (D) Qualitative indicators
 - Identification of promising business models, academic learnings
 - Feasibility studies and aroused interest generated pave the way for further projects of this kind
 - Identification of conclusions for legislation. Two main aspects have been considered for the use of the public grid in the framework of multilateral energy exchanges:
 - Reduction/abolish of utility fees,
 - Incentives for energy share in sector-coupling.

4.11 OxySteel

4.11.1 Project goals

- Energy efficiency and demand side management in steel production by the use of oxyfuel and CCU technology
- Identification of flexibilities and energy efficiency in process heat production
- Replacement of gas burners by oxy-fuel burners
- Reduction of the required electrical storages and support of the stability of the electrical power grid
- Demonstrator in the Breitenfeld Edelstahl AG steel plant

4.11.2 Solutions developed

- Oxyfuel

4.11.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

- (A) Climate dimension
 - reduced CO₂ emissions due to lower energy consumption
 - highest potential in combination with carbon capture and utilisation
- (B) Macro-economic dimension
 - investment costs
- (C) Resilience
 - reduced energy consumption (gas, electricity)
- (D) Qualitative indicators
 - process optimisation

In the first step, the scaling was carried out intra-sectorally from the site (Breitenfeld) to the steel industry in Austria and in the second step, the scaling was extended to the cement industry, where this developed oxyfuel technology can be applied as well.

Figure 8: Scaling steps for model solution oxyfuel

4.12 SANBA – Smart Anergy Quarter Baden

4.12.1 Project goals

- Conception of an energy network for the “Martinek barracks” in Baden with surplus heat from the neighbouring NÖM dairy
- Provision of scientific, technical and socio-economic know-how for the efficient planning and design of local energy networks
- Development of a simulation tool for the flexible planning of local energy networks
- Development of three scenarios for a future use of the “Martinek Barracks” (exclusive use of the historic buildings or with the additional new buildings)

4.12.2 Solutions developed

- Waste heat usage from the NÖM dairy with heat pump and thermal energy storage
- Feasibility study

4.12.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(A) Climate dimension

- Emission reduction due to waste heat usage and therefore energy savings

(B) Macroeconomic dimension

- Investment in heat pumps and thermal energy storage

(C) Resilience

- Energy savings and therefore reduced demand of energy import due to waste heat usage

(D) Qualitative indicators

- Feasibility study and aroused interest pave way for further projects of this kind

4.13 SBM_Ind – Smart Business Models for Industry

4.13.1 Project goals

- Identification of potential bottlenecks in the electrical grid and natural gas grids
- Assessment of the future demand for energy
- Identification of innovative business models that can address the challenges
- Examination of interests and needs of industrial companies regarding energy-related business models. Based on the research, four promising cooperative business models were developed.

4.13.2 Solutions developed

Based on the research findings, four cooperative business models were identified as promising solutions. These include:

- 1) Community grid platform with energy storage technology: This model leverages energy storage to create a community grid platform, ensuring efficient energy distribution and utilisation.
- 2) Selling hydrogen from surplus energy as fuel: Utilising surplus energy to produce and sell hydrogen as a fuel source, enabling a sustainable energy market and generating additional income.
- 3) Use of industrial waste heat: Harnessing industrial waste heat for heating purposes, promoting energy efficiency and reducing waste across economic sectors.
- 4) Energy Hub 4 Industry: Establishing a central hub to address energy-related queries and provide support to industrial and commercial entities.

4.13.3 Levers of Action and Scalability

(D) Qualitative indicators

- identification of promising business models, academic learnings

5 RESULTS

5.1 Qualitative results

In the context of the NEFI Impact Assessment, the outcome of the NEFI sub-projects are analysed both on a quantitative and qualitative manner. So far, the sub-projects Oxysteel, CE4T, EDCSproof, EDDY, HySteps, SANBA, SBM_Ind, InduGrid, Heat Highway, Greenbricks and Biochar4Industry have been assessed in detail and apart from the solutions already shown in the form of NEFI factsheets, the following **qualitative outcomes and general findings** are worth mentioning:

- **Digitalisation:** across a number of projects, it became evident that many industrial partners have little to no (time-resolved) data regarding the energy consumption of their processes. The installation of energy monitoring equipment and evaluation tools was highly appreciated and a first necessary step towards real time control, automation and thus the decarbonisation of the processes.
Risk to be addressed: Decrease in employment due to automation.
- **Environmental Responsibility:** apart from the obvious cost and climate benefits when reducing the CO₂ footprint, many NEFI partner organisations detected an improved acceptance of the business activity in the region and with the local population. Decarbonisation can in fact even become an important unique selling proposition. Stakeholder management and active communication of the project and its results and impact is therefore highly beneficial.
- **Feasibility and demonstration:** the first project is typically considered by the partners to be a trial run not only to demonstrate whether decarbonisation is technically and economically feasible but also to check the expertise of the NEFI research partners. After successful project completion, the industrial partners are enthusiastic to carry the decarbonisation project on to different sites.
It cannot be overestimated how relevant a fully working demonstration site is for the roll-out of (technological) solution. Industrial companies are typically highly skeptical regarding solutions that are not “off the shelf” especially if the feasibility has not been proven in the field or long-term data is unavailable.
- **Energy security and supply reliability:** expanding the use of regional energy sources at the supra-regional level stabilises domestic production and increases reliability of supply. By stabilising domestic production, optimising resource utilisation, and balancing supply and demand, this approach provides a resilient and sustainable energy system (Heat Highway).
- **Domestic production:** supporting domestic production within energy communities is a vital aspect of creating a sustainable and self-sufficient energy ecosystem by increasing the scale of installed photovoltaic systems, heating/cooling pipes for thermal exchange, energy storage units, charging infrastructure for electric vehicles, as well as through the conversion from oil heating to heat pumps in a company (InduGrid).
- **Optimisation:** process optimisation within the context of energy communities involves enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of energy production, distribution, and consumption. This can be achieved through various strategies, including the integration of advanced technologies, data analysis, and innovative management practices. In the InduGrid project, for example, the process was optimised during hardening through investigations and measurements.
- **Acceptance:** virtual demonstrator (3D simulation) demonstrates manageability despite the complexity of multiple players, communicate advantages, inform, motivate and tries to push implementation. Demonstration of new technologies is crucial, as it helps bridging the gap between innovation and widespread adoption. It is essential for proving their value, gaining stakeholder trust, collecting feedback and achieving market readiness. This process not only accelerates innovation adoption but also educates and engages potential users and supporters (Heat Highway).
- **Hurdles, barriers, framework conditions** identified:
 - According to the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios, carbon capture technologies are a key lever of action for a full industrial decarbonisation. However, Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) as well as Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) legislation and regulatory frameworks are still lacking (highly relevant for the penetration and full exploitation of the potential of the oxyfuel technology).
 - Regulatory frameworks related to the level of utility network charges and legislation concerning energy communities can pose barriers to the deployment of new energy

- communities and hurdles for the implementation of new business models (InduGrid, CE4T, SBM_Ind).
 - The long duration of the adjustment of the legal restrictions causes time delays in the implementation of some projects. For example, the implementation of multilateral energy exchanges in energy communities in regions with different network operators (InduGrid).
 - Regulatory approval procedures such as environmental impact assessments are often time-consuming processes. Faster procedures would reduce the barriers of planning green infrastructure projects (CE4T).
- Major infrastructure projects (e.g., wind turbines, PV) often face resistance from the local population. Stakeholder engagement increases acceptance and must be considered from the outset in such projects (CE4T).
- The preservation of historic buildings can pose challenges when undertaking necessary renovations especially with regard to decarbonisation efforts (SANBA).
 - Obstacles in obtaining permissions from all landowners and gaining regulatory approvals contribute to the project's complexity, along with significant investment costs and challenges. It is a call for political involvement (Heat Highway).
 - Confidentiality issues at a very early stage of the technology assessment, even within the non-disclosure agreements, have emerged as barriers to anticipating the mid-term usage of industrial excess heat from sustainable processes. Confidential data often poses significant challenges in obtaining and assessing information because it is restricted from public access to protect privacy, security, or proprietary interests. This can lead to incomplete datasets, hindering the ability to perform thorough and accurate assessments even among project partners, as well as in the context of Impact Assessment (Heat Highway).
 - Financial feasibility is sometimes an obstacle to the realisation of heat exchange projects, despite technical feasibility. One of the planned heat exchange sub-projects was not implemented due to negative economic feasibility. The costs associated with its implementation outweighed the potential benefits under current economic conditions. However, if gas prices increase significantly in the future, the project's viability may improve, allowing it to be revisited and contribute to climate neutrality (InduGrid).

5.2 Quantitative results

The quantitative results are shown in the following table:

Table 2: Quantitative results

Dimension	KPI	Result (cumulated 2025 to 2040)	Interpretation
Climate	$I_{CO_2e,tot}$	56 Mt CO _{2e}	Optimal roll-out of the project solutions result in the potential to save 56 Mt of cumulated CO ₂ emissions until 2040, which corresponds to 53% of the expected cumulated industrial CO ₂ emission until 2040 as calculated in the POI scenario (see Figure 9).
Macro-economic	$I_{me,tot}$	2.2 bn €	After full roll-out, the cumulated macroeconomic impact of the solutions assessed amounts to approx. 2.2 bn € mostly due to CAPEX and OPEX. In relation to the gross domestic product this seems negligible. However, it underlines that the NEFI solutions are cost-efficient. In the context of industrial decarbonisation, there are still low hanging fruits which have been addressed by the initial NEFI projects considered for this impact assessment.
Resilience	$I_{res,tot}$	97 TWh	After full roll-out, the NEFI solutions assessed have the potential to increase the independence from imported fossil fuels by reducing the total energy demand from imported fossil fuels by 97 TWh, which corresponds to 26% of the expected cumulated industrial total energy demand from imported fossil fuels until 2040 (see Figure 10).

The following charts present the results of the cumulated saved emissions and cumulated saved demand of imported energy by NEFI impact in comparison with the total emissions and energy demand, respectively of the NEFI POI scenario.

Figure 9: NEFI climate impact: Comparison of addressed cumulated emissions (turquoise) and total cumulated emissions in industry in Mt CO₂e (NEFI POI scenario).

Figure 10: NEFI resilience impact: Comparison of addressed cumulated final energy demand vs. total cumulated final energy demand of natural gas in industry in TWh (NEFI POI scenario).

For these potentials to be realised, the following conditions are essential:

- High TRL technologies need to be upscaled and implemented. This will require further substantial R&D to integrate them smoothly into existing processes, especially where core production processes need to be changed, e.g. oxysteel.
- Research and implementation support (e.g. RTI Initiative for Transforming Industry with FFG and KPC funding) need to go hand in hand and not only aim at single demonstration sites but also at industrial scale integration.
- Results need to be communicated through targeted channels such as trade fairs or industry magazines in order to effectively reach the relevant industry.

6 SUMMARY & OUTLOOK

In the context of the impact assessment, a stable and reliable methodology has been developed which is applicable to all NEFI sub-projects, technological and systemic solutions irrespective of their differences. In order to gain a full picture, it is essential to not only focus on the quantifiable impact in the form of e.g. climate or macro-economic KPIs but also to include qualitative factors. Moreover, NEFI is well aware that not each and every sub-project has the same (quantifiably) large economic or climate impact but nonetheless they are relevant in an overall research portfolio. The methodology of the impact assessment has been established in a way to evaluate on the one hand projects with a direct impact on quantitative KPIs (such as reduction of CO₂ emissions) and on the other hand projects with a more qualitative focus for instance projects dealing with business models, regulatory frameworks etc.

As the quantitative results show (see section 5.2), the NEFI solutions assessed so far already address a significant amount of the cumulated industrial CO₂ emissions. It must be noted that this does not provide a representative view of the entire model region. It is not expected that by the end of the project duration, 100% of the CO₂ emissions will be addressed. On the macroeconomic dimension, the results indicate that the first NEFI solutions address a relevant and cost-efficient lever of decarbonisation. Relatively moderate and manageable investments (CAPEX) of approx. 2 bn. € will lead to a significant 53% reduction of CO₂-emissions. Recent outcomes of the project Transform.Industry² estimated the costs for a total transformation of industry - depending on the scenario - to a range from 17.4 to 24.4 bn. €. In line with these findings, we anticipate that the first cohort of NEFI solutions addressed the “low-hanging”, hence cost-efficient, “fruits” while the full impact of NEFI will show a much higher macroeconomic effect and an approximation to the estimated cost effects of Transform.Industry.

The impact assessment methodology is now well-established and has thoroughly been tested with a broad variety of projects, covering all kinds of solutions (from technological to systemic) and across all industrial sectors. It is planned that the methodology will be applied to the remaining NEFI projects, once they have reached their completion, as well as through the newly funded innovation lab NEFI+ to all projects funded by the FTI initiative “Transformation of Industry”. Furthermore, the focus will be on contextualising the results within the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios. This feedback loop is highly relevant and valuable, allowing for robust and reliable scenarios to be developed. Dissemination and visualisation of the outcomes are planned as part of the newly established Virtual Industry Lab. A virtual industry showroom will be established utilising augmented or virtual reality applications. NEFI+ solution-based use cases as defined in the impact assessment will be implemented to visualise decarbonisation measures for industrial sites, in regional resolution.

The final results will be presented at the closing event (scheduled as per offer in Q4/2024).

² Transform.Industry is a project contracted by KLIEN to NEFI core partners AIT and MUL and other partners. Transform.Industry builds upon the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios and includes economic aspects and costs of the transformation of industry. The results of this project will be published in autumn 2023